

Research Article

**Knowledge of Non-Consensual Sex among Secondary School Students in Okrika
Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria**

Samuel, G.K* and Iwowari, Aminadoki
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port-Harcourt. P.O. Box 61 IAUE
Rumuolumeni, Port-Harcourt. *Corresponding Author Email:
gente.samk@gmail.com

Abstract

This study investigated the knowledge of Non-Consensual Sex (NCS) among secondary school students in Okrika Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. Three hypothesis were formulated. The study adopted the descriptive survey design. Six Hundred (600) Students were drawn from the 1,862 senior secondary school students in Okrika using multi-stage sampling procedure. The instrument for data collection was the questionnaire designed by the researcher titled Non-Consensual Sex Knowledge of secondary school students. The instruments were validated by 3 experts in reproductive health and health promotion. The reliability of the instrument was determined using the Kuder-Rechardson 21 method which gave a reliability coefficient of 0.8. The results of the study were that; age had a significant influence on the knowledge of NCS. ($df = 597, z = 7.17, P = 0.00$). Gender has a significant influence on knowledge of non-consensual sex ($df = 597, z = -580, P = 0.00$) and that religion significantly influences knowledge of non-consensual sex ($df = 597, z = 8.07, P = 0.00$). Based on the findings of the study some recommendations were made, which included NGOs, government and Health Educators at all levels should intensify health Education and awareness campaigns in schools with emphasis on the consequences of NCS. Religious leaders should incorporate NCS awareness in their teachings.

Keywords: Non-consensual Sex, Knowledge, Secondary School students, Rivers State, Nigeria.

Received: 14 March 2017

Accepted: 11 June 2017

Introduction

Non-consensual sex are sexual abuses, threats, intimidations, unwanted touching of erotic parts of the body, forced to viewing pornography, unwanted kiss, charmed to have sexual intercourse, drugged to have sexual intercourse, attempted rape and rape (Erulkar, 2004; Jaya, Hindin and Ahmed, 2007; Blythe, Olaleye and Ajuwon, 2011). It involves any form of sexually related advance against the will of the individual. Non-consensual sex implies that the individual does not want or consent to such sexual advances by the perpetrators. It embraces a wide range of unwanted sexual attempts, on the victim ranging from unwanted touching of erotic parts of the body such as; the breast, the buttocks, the thighs, unwanted sexual comments, forced embrace, unwanted kissing, sweet talking, verbal insistence, threats, intimidation, withholding economic support, use of drugs, charms, physical strength among others. Many students especially those females within age of 10 - 15 does not know the original definition or term to use to describe these unwanted sexual advances, so they tend to take it lightly with the perpetrators and this has led to them facing some problems associated to non-consensual sex without knowing the source of their problems. Whereas, a good knowledge about non-consensual sex at an early stage of a child especially to females who are vulnerable to non-consensual sex will help them speak out and fight against it. Ajuwon and Olaleye (2011), Erulkar (2004) have found out that the reasons why students experience these problems is as a result of poor knowledge. Therefore, this study is geared towards investigating the knowledge of non-consensual sex among senior secondary school students in Okrika Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Babara, Renate and Steffen (2003) studied men's report of non-consensual interactions with women in Germany using simple percentage, mean and standard deviation to describe the prevalence and impact of non-consensual sexual experience. The result showed that all the men had experimented sexual contact of which 90% were consensual and 10% non-consensual. A total of 90.2% of the sample had engaged in consensual intercourse, 91.5% reported consensual kissing, 10% non-consensual kissing, 27% non-consensual oral sex and the mean age of first intercourse was 16.5 (SD=1.95), the mean number of coital partners was 6.9 (SD=6.75).

Sex, be it consensual or non-consensual is the right of the man and the woman has no right to refuse it (Ryan, 2012). Kenyan Christians understood this fact, that is why it is not even justified or mentioned that the man raped a women (wife) even when she refused him sex and he forcefully had sex with her, hence Christians had little or no public case of rape compared to the Muslims who marry even minors (Ryan, 2012).

Cook and Mueheleshhard (2011) researched on men's self-report of non-consensual sexual activity ranging from unwanted kissing, petting or intercourse, they had engaged in because of physical or psychological pressure or from social expectations about male sexuality. Using the questionnaire, they asked if respondents had ever engaged in non-consensual sexual activity for any of 51 reasons they postulated. The questionnaire was administered to 507 men and 486 women. More women (97.5%) than men (93.5%) had experienced unwanted sexual activity. More men (62.7%) than women (46.3%) had experienced non-consensual intercourse. Using factor analysis, they grouped the 51 questionnaire items into 13 general reasons. Comparing percentage for men and women who had engaged in unwanted sexual activities, seven (7) different reasons were prevalent. Five (5) were more frequent for women and 2 for men. Those for men were peer pressure and popularity. The study further added that the situation was due to the double standard for male and female sexuality.

The South Africa Population Council (2004) researched on sexual coercion among men using the descriptive survey and a population of about 3,000 men and had the following results; 10% of the population reported to have had experienced non-consensual sexual intercourse such as unwanted sexual touch, made to touch someone sexually, to giving penetrative sexual intercourse.

Khan (2000) studied sexual violence among women in Bangladesh exploring the extent frequency and nature of violence among women. A sample of 1991 women was randomly selected from eight villages. The questionnaire, focus groups discussion and 23 case studies were conducted. The following results were obtained; 72% of women reported violence against them in the preceding 12 months. The most common and frequently reported forms of violence are scolding (reported by 40% of women), slapping 44%, severe beating 19% and forced sexual intercourse 15%. The study further documented a lot of factors for violence against women, especially sexually related violence which include sexual dissatisfaction, poverty, and household management inability among others.

Also in Bangladesh, studies by Zubairu Isa, Mukutar, Hadiza and Hamisu (2011) identified sexually related threats and intimidation among university undergraduates in Northern Nigeria especially sexually related threats and intimidation were as high as 29% of sexual violence. They further added that it decreases with increasing age it was high among age less than 20, 20 - 24 and less among those above 25 years old.

Peter-Kio, Ene-Bongili, Imaledo and Elechi (2013) investigated the knowledge of HIV/AIDS and sexual behaviour among secondary school students of selected secondary

schools in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria using two staged random sampling technique, four hundred (400) students were selected for the study. Data was collected using a semi structured self-administered questionnaire and analyses were done using descriptive statistics and chi-square statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The results were thus; the mean age was 16.3 ± 1.6 years, 68.7% were females, 31.3% were males, and $99.5\% \pm 3.6$. About half (51.0%) of the respondents had knowledge score greater than 50%. The study revealed a non-significant relationship between gender and knowledge of HIV/AIDS. However, more females (64.8%) compared to males (35.6%) had good knowledge of HIV/AIDS. More than a quarter (28.1%) of the respondents had sexual partners. Out of this, 39.4% did not use any form of protection during last sexual episode and mean age at sexual debut was 14.2 ± 3.3 years. The mean number of sexual partners was 1.5 ± 1 partner. Knowledge of HIV was high while risky sexual behaviour persists. The study concluded that behavioural change intervention including sex education among secondary students should be emphasized.

Imaledo *et al.* (2012) studied knowledge, perception and experience of non-consensual sex among undergraduate students of the University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. In the study, 300 students were selected using purposive sampling; pretested self-administered questionnaire was used to collect data. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and chi-square at 95% significant level. The mean age at first sexual intercourse was 5-9 years. Less than a quarter (16.3%) knew that their father had been beating their mothers. More than (32.9%) of the respondents were of the view that it is not proper for a man to report if he is forced to have sex by his girlfriend. 23.1% were of the view that non-consensual sex is part of relationship so it should be tolerated. Overall, majority had good knowledge of non-consensual sex with a mean knowledge score of 2.9 ± 1.7 , more female (58.6%) than male (41.4%) have positive perception about non-consensual sex. 22% of respondents agreed that their first sexual experience was non-consensual with 9.0% having their first experience with boyfriend/ girlfriend.

Akanle (2011) studied sexual coercion of adolescent girls in Yoruba land in Nigeria. Using a descriptive survey design and stratified random sampling technique. He drew a sample size of 475 adolescent girls consisting of 410 in school and 65 out of school. Data was analysed using simple percentage and chi-square. The results of the study were as follows; 30% of the respondents experienced unwanted sexual comments and invitation for sex, 28.5% of the respondents experienced suggestive remarks of sexual infraction; 18% of the respondents have been shown pictures to encourage them to have sexual intercourse. Unlimited sexual advances was reported by 23% of the respondents; 45% of the respondents have experienced unwanted touching and rape, 3.2%. They further

reported that teachers/students were mostly (90%) perpetrators of unwanted sexual advances among females.

Zubairu, Isa, Makurtar, Hadiza, and Hamisu (2011) studied prevalence and of gender-based violence (GBV) among female university students in Northern Nigeria using the descriptive study design. Simple random sampling was used to draw 300 students for the study. Result overall, showed that respondents admitted having ever experienced one or more forms of gender-based violence since joining the university. Of the students who experienced violence, 22.8% (N=65) experienced physical violence, 22.2% (N=62) reported sexual violence and 50.8% (N=1134) endured emotional and verbal violence. The result further shows that the experience of GBV varied by socio-demographic characteristics. By age, the prevalence was highest among students aged 20 – 24 years and lowest among the age group 25 – 29. The difference, however, was not statistically significant. Single students were more likely to have experienced GBV compared to those that have ever been married (62.3% vs 47.1% respectively, $P = 0.025$). Law students were least likely (50.6%) to experience violence compared to students from other faculties. In contrast, students from the faculty of social and management sciences were most at risk (71.4%) followed by medical students (58.0%) and students from the faculty of Education (54.3%), in decreasing order.

By ethnicity, non-Hausa/Fulani students were at increased risk of GBV as shown by a prevalence of 63.6% and 75.0% among Yoruba students and those from other tribes respectively. Nevertheless, Igbo students had the lowest prevalence of 50.0%, although they were quite few in the sample: Muslim students were less likely to experience GBV compared to students belonging to other religious faiths (55.8% vs 78.7% respectively, $P = 0.009$). Differences in experience of GBV by place of residence was also statistically significant, whereby students staying on campus had a prevalence of 69.9% compared to 51.7 among non-campus students ($P = 0.002$).

Statement of the problem

When an individual is compelled to engage in sexual activities against the will of the person, especially when the individual is raped, the victim stands the risk of contracting sexually transmitted diseases including HIV/AIDs and in most cases resulting to the death of the individual. The individual also suffers from economic losses as a result of financial commitment, energy and time expended for the treatment (if treatable) and the management of such conditions. The victim also suffers social maladjustment due to persistent pain from unwanted, unplanned and unintended pregnancy. The consequences if not properly handled with the highest form of medical and psychological measures could lead to death of the victim as a result of the disease contracted or suicide

due to inability to cope with the shame associated with the consequences of non-consensual sex.

In view of the consequences, problems and effects of non-consensual sex mentioned above; pre-informing the student about non-consensual sex either through seminars, class teaching, mass media etc. will enable them have a good knowledge about it, which will in-turn help to reduce non-consensual sex experiences amongst students thereby preventing or avoiding these consequences, problems and effects of non-consensual sex aforementioned.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the knowledge of non-consensual sex among senior secondary school students in Okrika Local Government Area of Rivers State. In specific terms, the study intends to;

1. Study the influence of age on knowledge of non-consensual sex among senior secondary students in Okrika Local Government Area of Rivers State.
2. Study the influence of gender on knowledge of non-consensual sex among senior secondary students in Okrika Local Government Area of Rivers State.
3. Study the influence of religion on knowledge of non-consensual sex among senior secondary students in Okrika Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Significance of the study

This study has many significant dimensions to it. It will provide enlightenment to the senior secondary school students by revealing what constitutes non-consensual, unwanted or sex against their will, which will help the students to reject all forms of non-consensual sexual approaches directed at them

The findings of this study will help showcase the need for health educators in the senior secondary schools to see non-consensual sexual activities among senior secondary school students as an area of need in health education.

The findings will also inspire health educators and researchers in public health and psychology to further research on non-consensual sexual activities among senior secondary school students and colleges as an area of need and so direct their research efforts into the consequences and the strategies for prevention of non-consensual sexual activities among students. The findings will also serve as a guide or reference material for researcher studying non-consensual sex and related researches. It will be a useful literature review, study design and methodology adopted for the collection and analysis of data.

It will further help school administrators to understand that there exist the problem of non-consensual sexual experiences among students hence, give or proffer measures to contain it by constituting panels, committees etc. to tackle cases of non-consensual sexual activities against students through the provision of suitable avenues for students to seek redress or complain when victimized

The findings will be beneficial to guidance counsellors, psychiatrist and social workers to understand the existence of non-consensual sexual experiences among students and further make them to design rehabilitation programmes and techniques of coping for victims of non-consensual sex.

The findings of this study will also help equip teachers, students and other individuals who could perpetrate the dastardly act to understand the existence of the possibility of contracting any of the sexually transmitted diseases including HIV/AIDs, the possibility of being sacked or suspended if found guilty after investigation

Research hypotheses

The following null hypotheses will be tested at 0.05 level of significance to guide this study;

1. There is no significant relationship between age and knowledge of non-consensual sex among senior secondary school students in Okrika Local Government Area of Rivers State.
2. There is no significant relationship between gender and knowledge of non-consensual sex among senior secondary school students in Okrika Local Government Area of Rivers State.
3. There is no significant relationship between religion and knowledge of non-consensual sex among senior secondary school students in Okrika Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Area of the study

This study will be carried out among senior secondary school students in Okrika Local Government Area of Rivers State. Okrika is a Port Town in Rivers State, Capital of the Local Government Area of the same name. It is situated in an Island just south of Port Harcourt, making it a suburb of the much larger city. It lies on the north of Bonny River and on Okrika Island 35miles (56km) upstream from the Bight of the Atlantic. It can be reached by vessels of 29 feet (9metres) or less.

Research design

This study adopted the descriptive survey design. This study is a descriptive survey because the researcher collected data from a large population of senior secondary school students in Okrika Local Government Area in Rivers State and described their knowledge of non-consensual sex without manipulating any variable of the study.

Population of the study

The population of the study comprises of senior secondary school students in Okrika Local Government Area of Rivers State. The population of senior secondary school students in Okrika Local Government Area of Rivers State is one thousand, eight hundred and sixty-two (1,862) students (Planning, Research and statistics, Rivers State Senior Secondary Schools Board, 2015)

Sample and sampling techniques

The sample size for this study consisted of six hundred (600) students drawn from the senior secondary schools in Okirka Local Government Area of Rivers State. Stratification based on class of students was carried out. Thirty-three (33) students were selected from SSI, 33 students from SSII and 34 students from SSIII. Simple Random sampling of balloting with replacements was used to select the respondents from each of the classes (SSI, SSII and SSIII). Ballot papers bearing Yes and No were put in a bag and students were asked to pick. A ballot bearing yes means that the respondent was selected and the instrument was given to the students. The ballot bearing No means students was not selected and the instrument was not given to the students. It is showed in Table 1 thus;

Table 1: Stratification based on class of students

NAME OF SCHOOLS	SAMPLE SELECTED			TOTAL NO. OF STUDENTS
	SS1	SS2	SS 3	
Okrika National Secondary School	33	33	34	100
Comprehensive secondary Kalio Ama	33	33	34	100
Government Girls Secondary School Okumgba Ama	33	33	34	100
Comprehensive Secondary School Okochiri	33	33	34	100
Comprehensive Secondary School Ogan Ama	33	33	34	100
Comprehensive Secondary School Okujagu Ama	33	33	34	100
Total Sample Size				600

Instrument for data collection

The instrument used for data collection was the questionnaire designed by the researcher, titled knowledge of non-consensual sex among senior secondary school students in Okrika Local Government Area of Rivers State. The instrument was made of two sections. Section A concentrated on the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents whereas section B dealt with the knowledge of non-consensual sex. The questionnaire return rate was hundred percent because all the questionnaire instruments were monitored during the filling.

Validity of the instrument

The instrument was validated by three experts in reproductive health and health promotion. Suggestions from these experts were incorporated in the final designing of the instrument. The instrument was therefore, certified to have both content and face validity.

Reliability of the instrument

The reliability of the instrument was tested on 60 respondents. From pilot testing of the instrument, 60 copies were subjected to Kuder -Richardson 21 method which is most appropriate for the instrument. A reliability coefficient of 0.8 was recorded which was high enough and can be used for the study.

Method of data analysis

Data was analysed using Z-test via the use of the statistical package for social sciences.

Results

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of Age on Knowledge of Non-consensual Sex among senior secondary school students in Okrika Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 2: Z-test Analysis showing Influence of Age on Knowledge of Non-consensual sex

Age(In Years)	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	z-value	P-value	Decision
10-14	103	5.65	2.28	597	-7.17	0.00	Significant H ₀ rejected
15 and above	496	7.77	2.81				

The findings of the study showed a significant influence of age on knowledge of non-consensual sex (df = 597, z - value = -7.17, p-value = 0.00). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

H₀₂: There is no significant influence of Gender on Knowledge of Non-consensual Sex among Senior Secondary School students in Okrika Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 3: Z-test Analysis showing Influence of Gender on Knowledge of Non-consensual Sex

Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	z-value	P-value	Decision
Male	156	7.51	2.06	597	-5.80	0.00	Significant H ₀ rejected
Female	443	7.36	3.06				

Findings of the study showed a significant influence of gender on knowledge of non-consensual sex (df = 597, z-value = -5.80, p-value = 0.00). The null hypothesis is rejected.

H₀₃: There is no significant influence of Religion on Knowledge of Non-consensual sex among senior secondary school students in Okrika Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 4: Z-test Analysis showing Influence of Religion on Knowledge of Non-consensual Sex

Religion	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	z-value	P-value	Decision
Christian	441	7.94	2.79	597	8.07	0.00	Significant H ₀ rejected
Muslim	158	5.92	2.42				

The findings of the study however revealed a significant influence of Religion on Knowledge of Non-consensual sex ($df = 597$, z -value = 8.07, p -value = 0.00). The null hypothesis is rejected.

Discussions of Findings

Age and knowledge of non-consensual sex

The findings of the study revealed a significant relationship between age and knowledge of non-consensual sex. The result of the findings revealed that senior secondary school students 385 (87.3%) aged 15years and above have more knowledge compared to those 58(12.7%) aged 10-14years. The finding is in agreement with the findings of Ajuwon *et al.*, (2011) who puts knowledge of sexual debut at 16years for both sexes (boys and girls). Vikran *et al.* (2001) who submitted that knowledge of sexual debut for both sexes is 16years, Zubairu et al (2011) who revealed that knowledge of prevalence of Gender Based Violence (GBV) commenced at aged 20 and above, Imaledo *et al.* (2012) who reported that 20% girls and 15% boys within the age range of 15-19 in school had knowledge of sexual coercion especially rape and Peter-Kio *et al.* (2013) who concluded that the mean age for non-consensual sex was 16years. The results of the finding is not in agreement with the findings of Imaledo *et al.* (2012) who submitted that students within the age range of 5 - 9 years are more knowledgeable on non-consensual sex and have had their first sexual intercourse. Aciemo (1990) also agrees that senior secondary school students below the age of 14years are more knowledgeable on issues of non-consensual sex. The similarities in the findings might be as a result of the level of exposure and information available to the students with the help of the social media such as Facebook, 2go, Twitter and WhatsApp, here they easily browse and view pornographic pictures. Other reason might be as a result of the appearance of secondary sexual characteristics which enlarged their quest for knowledge on the changes in the anatomy and physiology of their body. Conversely, the reason for the poor knowledge of non-consensual sex might be as result of parent refusal to give age appropriate sex education to their children below the age of 15years owing to the erroneous belief that they are not yet mature to manage such information. It is therefore imperative for the introduction of age appropriate sex education to the students in order to make them understand themselves and know how to manage the anatomical and physiological changes that may emerge during puberty. This will enable them make informed decision on sex related issues in an ethically, morally and socially acceptable manner. Legislations should be promulgated on the use of the social media and proper monitoring of activities of children should be made to check their excesses.

Gender and knowledge of non-consensual sex

The findings of the study revealed a significant relationship between gender and knowledge of non-consensual sex. The finding revealed that 326(73.7%) females have more knowledge of non-consensual sex compared to their male counterparts 117(26.3%). The finding is in congruence with the studies conducted by Imaledo *et al.* (2012) who submitted that majority of the female adolescents (58.6%) than male (41.4%) have good knowledge of non-consensual sex. Murray *et al.* (2006) also agrees that those women living in urban areas are more sexually active and have good knowledge of non-consensual sex compared to men in the same locality. Erulkar (2004) and Ramakrishna *et al.* (2005) also reported good knowledge of non-consensual sex among female adolescents and university undergraduate. However, the study is at variance with the findings of Ajuwon *et al.* (2011) where he submitted that males (52%) have good knowledge of non-consensual sex compare to females (48%). Ramakrishna *et al.* (2005) reported that the knowledge of non-consensual sex and transactional sex is very high among (60%) boys than (40%) girls in Bangalore, India. Erulkar (2004) who reported poor knowledge of non-consensual sex among teenagers and adolescent males. The reasons for the similarities in the findings may be that female students have more challenges in tacking their unmet needs especially in cases where their parents or guardians cannot afford those needs. This will certainly predispose them to their perpetrators who capitalize on their parents' poor socio-economic status to lure them with gifts and money in order to carry out their wicked act. Female students also constitute great percentage of street hawkers, house-helpers, victims of child trafficking and internally displaced persons (IDPs) which are the leading predisposing factors to non-consensual sexual advances such as sexual abuse, sexual assaults, sexual harassment, rape, unwanted touching, transactional sex, early sexual debut and other forms of sexual perversions. Conversely, it is seemingly cumbersome for people to believe that non-consensual sexual advances are made to males even when they are reported, except the male child is still a baby. These erroneous beliefs have made the male students not to speak out when they are abused sexually. It is expedient and very instructive for the authorities concerned to tackle the menace of human trafficking, street hawking, and other activities that will expose the students to non-consensual sex.

Religion and knowledge of non-consensual sex

The findings of the study revealed a significant relationship between Religion and Knowledge of Non-consensual Sex. The result of the findings revealed that Christians 350(79.4%) are more knowledgeable compared to Muslims 94(20.6%) on issues of non-consensual sex. The findings of the study is in agreement with the results of Makhaza

(2014) who submitted that parents with Christian affiliation were more likely to teach their daughters about abstinence and Chinnah *et al.* (2016) who submitted that Christians (62.35%) knew more about non-consensual rape than Muslims (37.7%). However, findings conducted by Ugwu (2012) is a negation to the results above where he deposited that Muslims were more knowledgeable on both contraceptives and non-consensual sexual issues than Christians but were unable to speak out because of the shame it attracts in the Islamic domain. The reasons for the similarities in findings might be that Christian parents inform their children more on the need to keep the bed undefiled in line with the provision of the Holy Bible which they believe. Conversely, the dissimilarity in the finding might be as a result of the fact that Muslims believe that non-consensual sex is a non-issue and do not give it attention. In the midst of all this, the truth remains that good knowledge of non-consensual sex is a panacea to unwanted pregnancy, premarital sex, early marriage, sexually transmitted infections etc. which is why the need for age appropriate sex education and sound religious teaching is irrevocable.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- 1) Government at all levels, non-governmental organizations, (NGO's), health educators and other relevant agencies should intensify health education at the senior secondary schools with emphasis on the consequences of non-consensual sex.
- 2) Curriculum planners and subject specialist should include sex education in the curriculum which should start from primary school and it should be age appropriate.
- 3) Religious leaders like the Imams and pastors should also discourage non-consensual sex and other forms of sexual perversions like indecent dressing in their teachings. This will help to reduce the incidence of non-consensual sex.
- 4) Government and should promulgate legislations against non-consensual sex and ensure that offenders are duly punished in order to serve as a deterrent to others.

Conclusion

There exists a significant relationship between age, gender, and religion have significant influence on knowledge of non-consensual sex. Thus; the study populations have more knowledge of non-consensual sex which is higher in females, Christians and those aged 15years and above. It takes the form of rape, showering of gifts and asking for sex in return, accepting sex for fear of hardship, unwanted touching of sensitive parts of the

body such as buttocks, thigh and forced kissing, threatening or intimidation of students for sexual reasons. There is the need for intervention among the study group.

References

- Aciemo, R. (1990): Risk Factors of Rape, Physical Assault and Post Traumatic Stress Disorders in Women: Examination of Differential Multivariate Relationship. *Journal of Anxiety Disorder*, 12:123-131.
- Agardth, A., Karen, O. & Ostergren, P. (2011). Experiences of sexual coercion and risky sexual behaviours among Ugandan students. *BMC Public Health*, (11): 527-532.
- Ajuwon, A. J., Olley, B. O., Akin-Jimoh, I. & Akintola, O. (2001). Experiences of sexual coercion among adolescents in Ibadan, Nigeria. *African Journal of Reproductive Health*, 12(4): 74, 936.
- Ajuwon, J. A. & Olaleye, O. S. (2011). Experiences of nonconsensual sex among students in Ibadan Nigeria. *Sierra Leone Journal of Biomedical Research*, 3(3): 175-183.
- Ajuwon, J. A. Olaleye, A. & Faro, O.J.U. (2011). Sexual behaviour and experiences of sexual coercion among secondary school students in three states in Northern Eastern Nigeria. *Biomedical Central Public Health*, (6) 310 – 315.
- Akanle, F. (2011). Sexual coercion of adolescent girls in Yoruba land of Nigeria. *Current Research Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(2): 132 – 138
- Archampong, E. & Baidoo, J. B. (2011). *Treatment of consent in sexual assault*. Available at www.thequalityeffect.org.
- Babara, K., Renate, S. & Steffen, B. (2003). Men's report of non-consensual sexual interactions with women. *Journal of Sexual Behaviour*, 30(2) 165 – 15.
- Chinnah, U. C., Lawoyin, T. O., Ilika, A. L. & Nnebne, C. C. (2016): Contraceptive Knowledge and Practice Among Senior Secondary School Students in Military Barracks. Nigeria: nepononline.com
- Cook, W.S. & Muhuelleshard, L. (2011). Men's report of unwanted sexual activity at <http://www.iustar.org/pss/3812822-Retrieved-30> September, 2011.
- Degue, S. & Dillilo, D. (2014): *Understanding perpetrators of non-physical coercion: Characteristics of those who cross the line*. Available at <http://digitalcommon.unl.edu/psychotacpub/126>.
- Erulkar, A. (2004). The experience of sexual coercion among young people in Kenya. *Int., Fain Prospect*, 34:182 – 198.

Firestone, J. M. & McElroy, M. W. (2003): *Key issues in the New Knowledge Management*. Retrieved from:

<http://www.gaoshan.de/kmchina/thesis.pnp%3.html> on 11/7/2015.

Hucker, A. S. (2007): *Sexual Sadispa: psychopathology theory*. New York: Cuiford Press.

Hunt, D. P. (2003): The concept of knowledge and how to measure it. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 4(1): 100-113.

Imaledo, A. J. Peter-Kio, O. B. & Asuquo, E. O. (2012): Pattern of risky sexual behaviour and associated factors among undergraduate students of University of Port Harcourt. *Pan African Medical Journal*, 17: 62-67.

Imaledo, J. A., Peter-Kio, O. B. & Asuquo, O. E. (2012). Knowledge, perception and experience of nonconsensual sex among undergraduate students of the University of Port Harcourt. *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research*, 2(2): 2005-2015.

Imaledo, J. A., Peter-Kio, O. B. & Asuquo, O. E. (2012). Pattern of risky sexual behaviour and associated factors among undergraduate students of University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. *Pan African Medical Journal*, 1937 – 1940.

Jaya, J., Hindin, M. J. & Ahmed, S. (2007). Adolescent reporting of sexual behaviour in randomized trial in urban India. Delhi. *A.M.J. Journal*, Pub.

Keziah, A. A. & Ajoku, L. I. (2013). *Foundations of curriculum development and implementation*. Port Harcourt: Pearl Publishers.

Khan, M.E. (2000). *Sexual violence in Bangladesh*. At [www.glibalinforum](http://www.glibalinforum.org) health.org
www.htt//pmanabv.com/health/4206-why-African-wMay13.2012

Makhaza, M. (2014): Knowledge and Use of Contraceptives Among Tertiary Education Student in South Africa. Rome-Italy MCSERC, Vol. 5 No. 10. Pp 502.

Mba, T. N. (2003). *Curriculum development concepts and processes*. Port-Harcourt: Crystal Publications.

Murray, N., Winfrey, W., Chatterji, M., Moreland, S., Dougherty, L., & Okonofua, F. (2006). Factors related to induced abortion among young women in Edo State, Nigeria. *Studies in Family Planning*, 37(4), 251-268. Doi:10,1111/j, 1728-4465-2006. 00104.x

Okafor, J.O. (2011). The collage of function health education for effective healthy decisions and health promotion Nigeria. Awka: J' Goshen Publishers and prints.

- Olaleye, O.S. & Ajuwon, A.J. (2011). Experiences of non-consensual sex among students in a tertiary in Ibadan. *Sierra Leone Journal of Biomedical Research*, 3(93) 175 – 183.
- Peter-Kio, O. B., Ene-Bongih, G. T., Imaledo, J. A. & Elechi, C. E. (2013): Knowledge of HIV/AIDS and Sexual Behaviour Among Senior Secondary School Students of Selected Secondary School in Port Harcourt local Government Area of Rivers State. *Continental Journal of Nursing Science*, 5(1): 1-12.
- Ramakrishna, J., Karrott & Radha, M.S. (2005) *Experiences of sexual coercion among street boys in Bangalo, India*. School of mental health and neuroscience (author)
- Ramiro, L. S. (2005). Physical intimacy and sexual coercion among adolescent intimate partners in Philippines. *Journal of Adolescent Research*, 20(4): 407-478.
- Rivers State Senior Secondary Schools Board (2015). Planning, Research and statistics, Rivers State Senior Secondary Schools Board(Author)
- Ryan, M. K. (2012): Further Evidence for Cognitive Component of Rape. Aggressive and Violent Behaviour, 9(6), 579-604. Doi: 10.1016/j.javb. 2003-05-001.
- Samuel, G. K. (2013). Perpetrators of non-consensual sexual experiences among undergraduates in Rivers State tertiary institutions. *Ozean Journal of Applied Sciences*, 6(2): 55-63.
- The South African Population Council (2004). Sexual coercion among men. Author Wellings, K., Kurar, N., Wendy, M. Sally, M., Rens, B., Mercer, C.T., *Wikipedia in Wikimedia Foundation Inc*. Last modified, July, 31, 2001.
- Ugwu, N. H. (2012): Knowledge and Use of Contraceptives Methods Among Youth in Abuja Metropolis Nigeria: Maitama.
- Websters (2006). *Dictionary of English Language*.USA: Trident.
- Willson, I. D (2002). *The nonsense of knowledge management information*. Retrieved from <http://informationRnet/ir/8-1/paper144.html> on 11/7/2015.
- World Health Organization (WHO) (2002). *World report on violence and health*. Geneva: WHO, www.flii.org/youthnet Retrieved November, 2011.
- Zubairu, I., Isa, S.A., Muktar, H.A., Hadiza, S.G., & Hamisu, M.S. (2011). Prevalence and conflate of Gender-based violence among female university students in Northern Nigeria. *African Journal of Reproductive Health*, 15, 123-133.